

Studies on applicability of Solomon's formalism on some Indian lignites and prediction of a few properties of the lignites from their FTIR data

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Abstract : In 1981 Solomon proposed a method of estimating aromatic carbon content of bituminous coals from their FTIR data and showed its correlation with the experimentally observed fixed carbon (FC). Present work aims to study the applicability of Solomon's method to five Indian lignites, viz. one Neyveli lignite and four Barmer (area Mahabarshivkur, Barmer, Rajasthan) lignite samples collected from four different locations. It is revealed that Solomon's method of ascertaining aromatic carbon content is also applicable to lignites with slight modification. Excellent correlation has been observed between aromatic carbon content C_{ar} and fixed carbon FC.

Moreover, distribution of hydrogen in Indian lignites are studied and their gasification ability are predicted using Pradier's method in terms of the ratio of integral intensity of stretching modes of $(CH_2/CH_2 + CH_3)$ in the region of 2800–3000 cm^{-1} . Observed bands are assigned according to Painter *et al.* Peculiarly enough, no band at or around 3030 cm^{-1} assigned to aromatic C–H stretching was observed in case of Neyveli and Barmer lignite B.

Keywords : FTIR, lignites, Solomon's formalism.

Lignite or brown coal occurring in number of forms, are distinguished by their physical properties. Compared to bituminous coal, lignite is considered as an inferior fuel owing to its higher volatile matter content and lower calorific value. Nowadays, it is not more considered as an ugly duckling in the hierarchy of coal, rather an eco-friendly source of energy owing to lower aromatic content. As a matter of fact, state of North Dakota, USA is generating its lion's share of electricity from the gasification of lignites. Moreover, lignites are often added with fertilizers, when applied in the fields, to make the fertilizers more effective, since lignites contain humic mass, O'Donnel¹, Mylonas and McCants².

On the basis of experimental evidence, it is widely accepted, that the aromatic carbon fraction of the coal is retained as fixed carbon (FC). FC therefore, should approximately be equal to aromatic carbon content of a coal sample. It should be noted in this context that in addition to aromatic carbon, FC contains certain amount of O, H, N and S, Solomon³. Similar correlation may exist between aromatic carbon content and FC, in case of lignite as well, although no such study is so far reported.

In 1981 Solomon³ derived aromatic carbon content of number of bituminous coals from their FTIR data and showed that a linear relation exists between FC and aromatic carbon content of bituminous coals. Prior to that Van Krevlen *et al.*⁴ (1957) suggested an empirical formula for obtaining FC in terms of aromatic carbon content of bituminous coal, given below :

$$FC = 1.023 \times C_{ar} \quad (1)$$

Twenty years have elapsed, no body has tried to apply Solomon's formalism to lignites to estimate their C_{ar} . On trying Solomon's formalism on lignites, the following difficulties are encountered :

(i) Accurate quantitative estimation of hydroxyl groups present in lignite (using FTIR) is extremely difficult.

(ii) Experimental data regarding stoichiometric ratio of aliphatic hydrogen to aliphatic carbon i.e. H_{al}/C_{al} are not adequately available.

A less branched aliphatic chain containing lignite should be a better agent for gasification, Mastalerz and Gliksun⁵. A lower value of the ratio of the integral intensity of stretching modes of $(CH_2/CH_2 + CH_3)$ in the region of 2800–3000 cm^{-1} indicates presence of a less branched

chain in a lignite sample, Pradier *et al.*⁶. We have studied extent of aliphatic branching in five lignites.

Methodology :

Solomon³ calculated aromatic carbon content of 43 american bituminous coal samples from their IR data. Lignites, however, contain longer aliphatic chains, evident from sharp peaks in the region of 2800–3000 cm⁻¹ observed in their FTIR spectra assigned as sp³CH₃, sp³CH₂, sp²CH₂ and sp²CH stretching modes. Apart from sp²CH all of them appear in doublet, viz. symmetric and asymmetric stretching. In practice some of them may be so weak that one can not definitely report their presence. In case of these five Indian lignites under study, only sp³CH₃ and sp³CH₂ (both sym. and asym.) modes are observed. Therefore, the following formalism was adapted to calculate the aromatic carbon content in these lignites :

In any lignite

$$H_{\text{total}} = H_{\text{al}} + H_{\text{ar}} + H_{\text{OH}} \quad (2)$$

where, H_{total} = total amount of hydrogen present in a lignite (to be obtained from ultimate analysis), H_{al} = total amount of aliphatic hydrogen present in a lignite sample, H_{ar} = total amount of aromatic hydrogen present in a lignite sample, H_{OH} = total amount of hydroxylic hydrogen present in a lignite sample (most of which is phenolic in character).

Some hydroaromatic (six-membered alicyclic) compounds may also be present. But C–H stretching frequencies of the hydroaromatic part is also observed in the same region where aliphatic C–H stretching modes are observed, Finar⁷. So, one can not differentiate between these two from the FTIR studies. No doubt, some –CHO, –COOH groups are attached to the periphery of the carbon network. In case of these lignites those are either absent or their presence is negligibly small.

Estimation of concentration of H_{OH} from FTIR data is a tricky proposition, since lignites as well as KBr used to prepare pellets absorb water, which contribute a lot to the band at about 3400 cm⁻¹ assigned to hydroxyl groups. Solomon and Carnelo⁸ have discussed in detail how to do away with the effect of absorbed water and how to estimate quantitatively the concentration of hydroxyl groups in coal macerals using FTIR. Proposed method requires prolong heating of KBr pellets at 175 °C. But lignites contain longer aliphatic chains and are prone to degrade under such condition, Sarkar⁹. We have tackled this problem other way round.

Majumder¹⁰ in 1984 proposed a model molecular for-

mula for lignites. One can calculate from this model what percentage of oxygen is present in form of –OH groups. Once this is known, one can calculate H_{OH} using the concept that one g-atom of oxygen is attached to one g-atom of hydrogen in –OH groups. It is found from Majumder¹⁰ model that in case of lignites 44% of total oxygen (obtained from ultimate analysis by difference) is present in form of H_{OH}.

Now, one can proceed in the following manner to calculate H_{al} and hence the concentration of aromatic carbon C_{ar} in lignites.

Rearranging eq. (2) we have

$$H_{\text{al}} = H_{\text{total}} - (H_{\text{ar}} + H_{\text{OH}}) \quad (3)$$

Now according to Brown and Ladner¹¹ in a coal or lignite sample

$$\epsilon_{\text{ar}}/\epsilon_{\text{al}} = 0.5 \quad (4)$$

combining eq. (3) and eq. (4) one can deduce that

$$H_{\text{al}} = (H_{\text{total}} - H_{\text{OH}}) / (1 + k/0.5) \quad (5)$$

where $k = OD_{\text{ar}}/OD_{\text{al}} = (\epsilon_{\text{ar}}/\epsilon_{\text{al}}) \times (H_{\text{ar}}/H_{\text{al}})$

OD_{ar} and OD_{al} are the optical densities of the aromatic and aliphatic C–H stretching obtained from the absorbance measured at 3030 and 2920 cm⁻¹, after proper background corrections, Brown and Ladner¹¹. H_{ar} and H_{al} are concentration of aromatic and aliphatic hydrogen in lignite samples under study.

In order to apply Solomon's formalism to lignites, one requires the knowledge of stoichiometric ratio of H_{al}/C_{al} of lignites. This ratio H_{al}/C_{al} for Indian bituminous coals was reported by Majumder *et al.*¹² to lie between 1.72–2.00. Other worker's of different countries reported this ratio to be around 1.8^{13,15}. Solomon³ himself made use of these values to evaluate C_{ar} of several American coals, Solomon³, however, did not take into account contribution of the alicyclic part in Majumder *et al.*'s work. As regards FTIR data are concerned it is extremely difficult, if not impossible to differentiate between six-membered alicyclic C–H stretching and aliphatic C–H stretching (reason mentioned earlier).

From Majumder's model¹⁰ one can calculate H_{al}/C_{al} ratio and this was found to be H_{al}/C_{al} = 1.51 (Ref. 10).

Alternatively, one can obtain H_{al}/C_{al} ratio from the experimental work of Majumder *et al.*¹². From Table 4 of Majumder *et al.*¹², for lignites H_{al}/H = 0.16 and H_{ha}/H = 0.55. From the same table C_{al}/C = 0.16 and C_{ha}/C = 0.22, where suffix al and ha stands for aliphatic and

hydroaromatic (six-membered alicyclic) part. Since we are concerned with FTIR data we are getting a cumulative effect of both, viz. aliphatic and hydroaromatic C–H stretching.

For FTIR data

$$H_{al}/H = 0.16 + 0.55 = 0.71 \text{ and } C_{al}/C = 0.16 + 0.22 = 0.38.$$

$$\text{Therefore } H_{al}/C_{al} = (0.71/0.38) \times (H/C)$$

From Table 2 Majumder *et al.*¹² H/C (atomic ratio for lignite) = 0.78.

Therefore, $H_{al}/C_{al} = (0.71/0.38) \times 0.78 = 1.457$ (Ref. 12).

Next C_{ar} was computed using Solomon's formalism³ written below

$$C_{ar} = C_{total} (12/x) H_{al} \quad (6)$$

where $x = H_{al}/C_{al}$ stoichiometric ratio. We have made use of experimentally observed H_{al}/C_{al} ¹⁰ as well as H_{al}/C_{al} calculated from Majumder model¹² and compared the C_{ar} obtained using both the data with FC (see Table 3). A linear relation was observed between FC and C_{ar} obtained using both the H_{al}/C_{al} .

Moreover, in case of each lignite, overlapping bands in the region 2800–3000 cm^{-1} (essentially C–H stretching) are deconvoluted to obtain the contribution of each overlapping mode, viz. sp^3CH_3 and sp^3CH_2 , both symmetric and asymmetric modes, so as to understand relative abundance of hydrogen configuration, i.e. $=\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{CH}$, or $-\text{CH}_3$ which of these are present and to what extent and also the nature of hybridisation present in these lignites. In each case ratio of the integral intensity of $(\text{CH}_2/\text{CH}_2 + \text{CH}_3)$ is calculated, which is a measure of extent of aliphatic chain branching, Pradier *et al.*⁶. Area of each deconvoluted bands were measured and hence the ratio, mentioned above. A less branched chain containing lignite is naturally a better material for gasification compared to those containing highly branched chain, Mastalertz and Glikson⁵.

Table 1. Proximate analysis data (% air dried)

Sl. no.	Sample	Moisture	Ash	VM	FC
1.	Barmer lignite A	30.2	4.3	35.2	30.3
2.	B	28.6	3.2	37.6	31.2
3.	C	27.2	5.2	37.5	30.1
4.	D	32.3	3.8	35.1	28.8
5.	Neyveli lignite	12.50	6.2	45.65	35.65

Table 2. Ultimate analysis data (air dried basis)

Sl. no.	Sample	C (in %)	H (in %)	S (in %)	N (in %)
1.	Barmer lignite A	47.3	3.27	0.60	0.51
2.	B	49.75	3.47	1.92	0.58
3.	C	50.23	3.43	1.77	0.51
4.	D	47.06	3.02	1.73	0.50
5.	Neyveli lignite	58.1	4.07	0.49	1.56

Experimental

Table 1 and Table 2 depicts results of proximate and ultimate analysis of five lignites, of which data of Neyveli lignite were taken from Subramaniam¹⁶ and those of four Barmer lignites were obtained from the Central Fuel Research Institute, Dhanbad.

FTIR spectra of five lignite samples under study are recorded using a Nicolet FTIR spectrophotometer (model no : MagnaIR 750) in the following fashion. First 50 scans are coadded. Next, spectra of five raw lignites are recorded with 4 cm^{-1} resolution. To do away with the effect of mineral matters present in lignites, Painter *et al.*¹⁷, a low temperature ash (LTA) of each lignites are made and their spectra are recorded in a similar fashion. Next a difference spectra of raw lignite and that of their respective LTA are obtained. It should be mentioned in this context that the amount of lignite and its LTA are so adjusted that in each difference spectrum approximately the effect of 1 mg of organic matter present in lignite is observed.

Fig. 1 shows FTIR of five lignites and Fig. 2 shows FTIR spectrum of raw Barmer lignite B and that of its

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of (a) Barmer lignite A, (b) Barmer lignite B, (c) Barmer lignite C, (d) Barmer lignite D and (e) Neyveli lignite.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) Barmer lignite B, (b) low temperature ash of Barmer lignite B and (c) difference of (a) and (b)

LTA and their difference Fig 3 shows 2nd derivative of the spectrum obtained from the subtraction of the spectra of the LTA of Neyveli lignite from that of raw Neyveli

Fig. 3. Second derivative of the difference spectrum of Neyveli lignite and its low temperature ash

lignite, to show, beyond any doubt that no band at or around 3030 cm^{-1} assigned to aromatic C-H stretching is observed

Analysis of FTIR data

Absorbance at 2920 and 3030 cm^{-1} are determined after linear background correction. Respective optical densities are calculated to obtain OD_{ar}/OD_{al} and hence H_{ar}/H_{al} for three lignites viz Barmer A, Barmer C and Barmer D lignites and C_{ar} are computed using eq (6), depicted in Table 3

Fig 4. Resolution of the infra red stretching bands in the region of $2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ Taken from Fig 2(c) i.e. difference spectrum of Barmer lignite B and its LTA. The deconvoluted modes are labeled as (1) sp^3CH_2 (sym), (2) sp^3CH_2 (sym) (3) sp^3CH_2 (asym) and (4) sp^3CH_2 (asym)

Fig 4 shows constituent C-H stretching bands obtained after deconvolution of the overlapping bands assigned to sp^3CH_3 and sp^3CH_2 (sym and asym) stretching in the region of $2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of Barmer lignite B (actually taken from the difference spectra i.e. from Fig 2(c)). Deconvolution was achieved using non-linear least-square fit, Maddams¹⁸. After linear background correction, each overlapping band is fitted with a pseudo-Voigt profile and subjected to least square fitting. Area of each deconvoluted modes were measured. This was done to understand nature of hybridisation present in these lignite and to understand relative abundance of each hydrogen configuration and hence their extent of aliphatic chain branching, Pradier *et al*⁶

Bands observed in five lignites are assigned according to Painter *et al*¹⁷. Aromatic C-H stretching occurs between $3010\text{--}3080\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in most of the organic compounds but for coal macerals, lignite etc they usually appear at or around 3030 cm^{-1} , Painter *et al*¹⁷. It should be mentioned in this context that 1033 and 1275 cm^{-1} bands are assigned as phenoxy -OH and alcoholic -OH respectively according to Painter *et al*¹⁷. However, we can not rule out the possibility of presence of ether linkage. Although low-temperature carbonization by-products of Neyveli lignite are methanol and phenol, ether may, however be retained in the tar. Solomon *et al*¹⁹ have reported presence of ether in the tar obtained as pyrolysis product of lignite above 400°C . Solomon²⁰ has assigned number of bands in the region of $1000\text{--}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as ether. Painter *et al*¹⁷ have strongly argued against such assignment. Majumder *et al*'s¹⁰ model of bituminization of lignite proceeds through condensation polymerisation of phenan-

Table 3. Correlation between C_{ar} (obtained from FTIR data) and FC

Sample	H_{ar}/H_{al}	C_{ar} derived from FTIR data using exp H_{al}/C_{al} (Ref. 12)	C_{ar} derived from FTIR data using H_{al}/C_{al} calculated from Ref. 10	FC (proximate analysis) /	Gross calorific value (using Gault's formula) kcal/kg
Barmer lignite A	0.11	32.10	32.63	30.3	5582
B	0.00	31.24	31.86	31.2	5743
C	0.09	32.14	32.58	30.1	5671
D	0.13	33.99	34.42	28.8	5479
Neyveli lignite	0.00	32.76	33.54	35.65	6185

threne units involving ether groups attached to the phenanthrene moiety. Considering these, one can not rule out possibility of presence of ether linkage in Indian lignites.

Summary :

In this paper we have studied :

(i) Distribution of hydrogen in five lignites : All of them are rich in aliphatic hydrogen. The H_{ar}/H_{al} ratio varies from 0.09 to 0.13. Neyveli and Barmer lignite B does not contain any aromatic hydrogen evident from the absence 3030 cm^{-1} band (see Fig. 3). This is apparently confusing that we are calculating C_{ar} of a substance which does not contain any aromatic hydrogen. Lignites are composed of phenanthrene units connected with each other through ether linkage, Majumder *et al.*¹⁰. Majumder *et al.* suggested that each phenanthrene moiety are highly substituted. It is quite possible that in case of Neyveli and Barmer lignite B phenanthrene units are completely substituted by functional groups like $-CH_3$, $-C_2H_5$, $-OH$, $-OCH_3$ etc. and that is why we observed no bands at or around 3030 cm^{-1} . But in both the cases a band is observed at or around 1610 cm^{-1} assigned to aromatic ring stretching. This explains the riddle that the aromatic moiety is present but no aromatic hydrogen. Long ago, Bent and Brown²¹ reported absence of 3030 cm^{-1} band in the IR spectra of Cannock Wood shallow exinite and Markham Main Barnsley exinite.

Some hydrogen is present as phenolic $-OH$ along with traces of alcoholic $-OH$, $-CHO$ and $-COOH$. However, nothing could be said about presence of alicyclic hydrogen from the FTIR studies.

(ii) Hybridisation type : Resolution of overlapping

bands in the region of 2800–3000 cm^{-1} clearly shows only sp^3 type of hybridisation is predominant in all the cases under study. In case of Barmer lignite A, C and D some sp^2 (aromatic) type is also present (as regards hydrogen atoms attached to carbon atoms are concerned).

(iii) Correlation between C_{ar} and FC and computed calorific values : Excellent correlation between C_{ar} (calculated from FTIR data using H_{al}/C_{al} from experimental data¹² as well as those computed from Majumder's model¹⁰) and FC of the lignites under study are observed and this is shown in Table 3 along with calorific values computed using Gault's formula⁹, written below

$$C_G = 82FC + aV$$

where, C_G = gross calorific value (in kcal/kg), FC = fixed carbon, V = volatile matter, a = a constant dependent upon V.

In each case exact value of constant 'a' is determined by interpolation technique.

There are other formulae as well to calculate C_G but these are of limited use because heat of formation of coal/lignite is neither zero nor constant⁹. However it provides some insight about the quality of the solid fuel under study.

(iv) Finally we have predicted gasification ability of lignites in terms of their extent of aliphatic chain branching. The ratio of integral intensity bands responsible for CH_2 and $(CH_2 + CH_3)$, i.e. $(CH_2/CH_2 + CH_3)$ is a measure of extent of aliphatic chain branching, Pradier⁶. A lower value of this ratio suggests lesser chain branching. A less branched chain containing lignite is a better agent for gasification than a more branched one. Table 4

shows ($\text{CH}_2/\text{CH}_2 + \text{CH}_3$) ratio for five lignites. One can predict in terms of this ratio and calorific values shown in Table 3 that Neyveli lignite is the best materials for gasification compared to other four lignites. Absence of aromatic hydrogen also suggests that it will burn with less sooty flame. The properties of the gas obtained from low temp. carbonisation of Neyveli lignite is as follows⁹ :

Specific gravity (referred to air) : 0.6

Calorific value : 6500 kcal/Nm³

Composition (in percent) : CO_2 , 4.0; C_nH_m , 4.0; CO , 7.0; H_2 , 33.0; $\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+2}$, 45.0; N_2 , 7.0.

No data regarding gasification of Barmer lignites is available. However, it is evident from Tables 3 and 4, that among the Barmer lignites we studied, Barmer lignite B counts best as a potential source of gas generating material.

Table 4. Study regarding extent of aliphatic chain branching (methodology explained in the section Summary)

Sample	Ratio of the area of ($\text{CH}_2/\text{CH}_2 + \text{CH}_3$)
Barmer lignite A	0.91
B	0.88
C	0.89
D	0.94
Neyveli lignite	0.86

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